

range 2.18–44.8 μg in 10 ml of the final solution. The solution containing 22.4 μg of iron gave a mean absorbance of 0.280 when measured in a 1 cm cell with a relative standard deviation of 0.71%. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were calculated to be $0.70 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.008 \mu\text{g Fe/cm}^2$ respectively.

Interference: The interference of various ions was studied. Generally, 10 mg of alkali and 1 mg of metal ion were added individually to iron solution. Among the anions examined, only fluoride and EDTA interfered. Among the metal ions studied, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} interfered. Cobalt was masked by adding 5% sodium cyanide, while nickel complex was broken by heating with 2M HCl and the interference due to palladium was removed by extracting the palladium-cyclohexylthioglycolate complex at low pH (pH 4.5).

Analysis of alloys: A solution of the alloy (50–100 mg) was prepared in aqua regia. An aliquot was taken, treated with 10% hydroxylamine hydrochloride (4 ml) and extracted by the given procedure. Cobalt was masked with 5 ml of 5% sodium cyanide and nickel complex was broken by heating with 2M HCl. The interference due to palladium was removed by pre-extracting at pH 4.5 and the iron content was determined by the given procedure. Five determinations were made for each alloy and the results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF IRON IN ALLOYS

Alloy	Certified composition of the alloy %	Amount of iron taken μg	Amount of iron found μg	Average μg	Relative standard deviation %
Steel 33rd (NBS)	Fe, 90.3 ; Ni, 2.38 ;	18.06	18.00	18.02	0.22
	Cr, 0.32 ;		18.06		
	C, 2–3 ;		18.08		
	Mn, 0.68 ;		18.00		
	Si, 1.63 ;		18.00		
	Cu, 1.54				
Stainless steel no. 306	Fe, 70–70 ;	28.00	28.2	28.14	0.47
	Cr, 16.5 ;		28.3		
	Ni, 12.0 ;		28.0		
	Mo, 2–3		28.0		
			28.2		

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Cyclopentane-spiro-2'-(1-phenyl-2',4'-dithio)-s-triazine as a Chromogenic Reagent for Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper(II)†

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Manuscript received 23 April 1990, revised 16 July 1990, accepted 20 October 1990

LITERATURE reports the use of thiotriazines as chromogenic reagents for the determination of copper(II)^{1,2}. The present work describes a simple method for the extraction spectrophotometric determination of copper(II) using cyclopentane-spiro-2'-(1-phenyl-2',4'-dithio)-s-triazine (CPSPDTT) as the reagent.

Experimental

CPSPDTT was prepared according to the described method³ and was recrystallised from ethanol to get analytically pure compound, m.p. 186–87°, mol. wt. 277. The reagent was found to be stable at room temperature at least for two months. A 0.002 M solution of CPSPDTT in dimethyl formamide was used. Standard stock solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A.R.) and was standardised⁴. A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic spectrophotometer was used for all spectral determinations. pH-measurements were made using Control Dynamics digital pH meter (C.D. Instruments).

To an aliquot of the solution containing 5–50 μg of copper(II) was added phosphate buffer (5 ml) of pH 7.0, followed by dilution with distilled water to 25 ml. To the mixture was added 0.002 M CPSPDTT (2 ml) in DMF followed by the addition of toluene (10 ml). After equilibration for 30 s the toluene layer was separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured at 410 nm against toluene as reference.

Results and Discussion

Toluene extract of the copper complex showed maximum and steady absorbance over the pH range 5.5–12.5. All other examinations were carried out at pH 7.0 using phosphate buffer as it was found suitable. From various solvents studied toluene was found to be most suitable for extraction of the complex.

Intense yellow coloured extracted complex exhibited maximum absorbance at 410 nm. At similar conditions, the reagent blank practically did not absorb above 390 nm. Reagent concentration study showed that 2 ml of 0.002 M CPSPDTT was sufficient to extract 40 μg of copper(II) in a single

† Presented at the 25th Annual Convention of Chemists, Calcutta, 1988.

operation. No diverse effect was observed till a 20-fold excess of the reagent and 50% DMF concentration in aqueous phase. Both mole-ratio and slope methods indicated the formation of 1:2 (metal: ligand) complex under the experimental conditions. System was found to obey Beer's law over the range 5–50 μg of copper(II).

The effect of foreign ions on copper(II) determination was studied at 2% tolerance limit. In the estimation of 20 μg copper(II), the following ions did not interfere when present in amounts (μg shown in parenthesis): Ni^{II} (400), Co^{II} (260), Hg^{II} (210), Bi^{III} (120), Mn^{II} (120), Cd^{II} (30), Ag^{I} (210), Cr^{VI} (200), Al^{III} (40). No interference was observed even after 6000 μg each of V^{V} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} , but Zn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Pb^{II} interfered seriously. When the determination was made at pH 12.0 more than 6000 μg of Al^{III} was tolerated. Ag^{I} and Hg^{II} were tolerated upto 1200 and 900 μg respectively when 10-fold excess CPSPDTT was used. Among the anions tested, the presence of more than 500-fold excess of nitrate, sulphate, iodide, bromide, fluoride, carbonate, thiocyanate and acetate had no diverse effect. Thiosulphate (270), persulphate (1100), citrate (40) and oxalate (150) were tolerated, but EDTA interfered seriously.

The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were calculated to be $1.08 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.006 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The average of 10 determinations of 20 μg copper(II) in 10 ml of toluene was 19.97 μg with standard deviation of 0.003. The method was applied for synthetic mixture of aluminium alloy having composition: Cu, 4.10; Fe, 0.43; Mn, 0.19; Ni, 1.93; Si, 0.29; Mg, 0.16%. The determination of copper(II) was carried out at pH 12, as aluminium(III) did not interfere at this pH. The mean of three determinations of the amount of copper was found to be 4.07%. The present method was found to be simple, rapid and precise. The total operation for each run required not more than 10–12 min.

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A Rapid Ultraviolet Spectrophotometric Method for Simultaneous Determination of Nitrate and Nitrite in Potable Waters

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Manuscript received 21 December 1989, revised 26 July 1990, accepted 24 September 1990

NITRITE when correlated with other forms of nitrogen in water can provide an index of organic pollution¹. Also, nitrite reacts with secondary

amines to form nitrosamines, many of which have been reported to be carcinogenic². Nitrate causes a disease in infants called methaemoglobinemia³. Innumerable methods have been reported for the estimation of nitrite⁴ and nitrate⁵ in water. Wetters and Uglum⁶ determined nitrate and nitrite from the same solution by uv spectrophotometry but at different wave-lengths. Nitrate has been reported to absorb at 220 nm and a method for its estimation has been adopted by American Public Health Association⁷. It has been observed that nitrite too similarly absorbs at the same wave-length but this absorption is suppressed by about 90% on treatment with 1.0 N hydrochloric acid and digestion for 5 min. This quantitative nature of suppression has been exploited here to determine nitrate and nitrite simultaneously at the same wave-length in potable waters where the level of interfering elements and organic matters which absorbs in uv region are appreciably low. This method has been successfully applied in the determination of nitrate and nitrite simultaneously in some natural well waters of Shillong city.

Experimental

A Varian 634-S double beam digital spectrophotometer was used.

1.0 N HCl (A.R.) was used. Stock nitrate solution (1 ml = 100 μg $\text{NO}_3 - \text{N}$) of potassium nitrate (A.R.) was prepared in distilled water and standard nitrate solution (1 ml = 10 μg $\text{NO}_3 - \text{N}$) was prepared by proper dilution. Stock nitrite solution (1 ml = 250 μg $\text{NO}_2 - \text{N}$) of sodium nitrite (A.R.) was prepared in distilled water and standard nitrite solution (1 ml = 10 μg $\text{NO}_2 - \text{N}$) was prepared by proper dilution.

Procedure: In step-I, a suitable aliquot containing 0–250 μg of nitrogen (NO_3/NO_2) was diluted to 50 ml and its absorbance for 220 nm against distilled water was measured. In step-II, the same amount of aliquot of the sample was taken and 1.0 N HCl (1.0 ml) was added and digested for 5 min. The solution was cooled to room temperature and made upto 50 ml and its absorbance was measured (220 nm) against distilled water as above. A calibration curve was prepared in the range 0–350 μg N.

Results and Discussion

Both nitrate and nitrite in water samples absorb together at 220 nm. The absorbance obtained from the step-I is due to nitrate and nitrite together. The absorbance obtained from the step-II is due to nitrate and 10% of nitrite.

The suppression of nitrite absorption due to the addition of hydrochloric acid remains constant above 25 μg nitrogen per 50 ml upto a concentration of 250 μg nitrogen. Below this concentration the suppression of nitrite absorption is not constant, therefore nitrite, if present below a concentration of 20 μg nitrogen per 50 ml, can accurately be